

ASCERTAINMENT OF THE CHANGE OF THE DUCTILITY IN CORRODED STEEL SPECIMENS BY EXPERIMENT

Antonio Shopov

Department “Strength of materials”, Technical University of Sofia –
8, “Kliment Ohridski” blvd., Sofia, 1000, Bulgaria, European Union

Borislav Bonev

Department “Microelectronics”, Technical University of Sofia –
8, “Kliment Ohridski” blvd., Sofia, 1000, Bulgaria, European Union

ABSTRACT

The studies of the ductility of the materials date back to ancient times. The basic values of the stress-strain diagram, which determines the groups in the main zones - the elastic zone, the yield zone, the strengthening zone and the fracture zone, are known. There are main construction steel elements always where corrosion is at an advanced stage. The corrosion of construction steel is an inevitable process. The negative consequences that indicate the corrosion of the steel elements have been partially established and opportunities for solving them should be sought. We conducted an experiment to determine how the ductility and main values of the stress-strain curve of corroded steel samples changed. We used S355JR steel and applied a galvanostatic electrochemical accelerated corrosion method. After that, we performed a tensile test of the samples, we took the values from the stress-strain diagrams and we calculated how the basic stress-strain values and the corresponding ductility changed. We used the stochastic method to process the results. We have come to the conclusion that corrosion affects the basic values, the ductility and the structural change of the material and when (and if) it is elastic-plastic, according to the stress-strain diagram, it is transformed into brittle material.

Key words: ductility, corrosion, electrochemical accelerated corrosion method,

Cite this Article: Antonio Shopov and Borislav Bonev, Ascertainment of the Change of the Ductility in Corroded Steel Specimens by Experiment, International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology, 10(01), 2019, pp. 1551–1560

<http://www.iaeme.com/IJCIET/issues.asp?JType=IJCIET&VType=10&IType=01>

1. INTRODUCTION

The basic definition of ductility is the measure of the ability of the material to undergo significant plastic deformation before rupture, which may be expressed in percentages during the processes of elongation or area reduction, while undergoing a tensile test [1-2]. Ductility is particularly important concerning steel as materials that crack, break or shatter under stress, cannot be manipulated using metal-forming processes such as hammering, rolling, drawing or extruding [1-2]. High degrees of ductility occur in steel elements, which are found predominantly in metals, leading to the common perception that metals in general are ductile. In metallic bonds valence shell electrons are de-localized and shared between many atoms [1-2]. The de-localized electrons enable metal atoms to slide past one another without being subjected to strong repulsive forces that would cause other materials to shatter [1-2]. Ductility can be quantified by the fracture strain, which is the engineering strain at which a test specimen fractures during an uniaxial tensile test [1-2]. Another commonly used measure is the reduction of the area of fracture [1-2]. The ductility of construction steel varies depending on the constituents of the alloy [1-2]. The increase in the levels of carbon decreases [1-2]. Some authors make a note that the mechanism for determining mechanical properties resulting from corrosion and stress corrosion is also complicated by additional factors such as energy accumulation, environmental impact, action of sulphate-reducing bacteria, electrochemical and destructive processes in a structural layer [3], that means ductility it would be depended from exactly the same factors. According to some regulations, every construction element from steel need to have a certain ductility, but when the corrosion is occupied (Figure 1) there are not guarantee that ductility is not changed. Some researchers study an altering the mechanical properties or ductility [4-18, 22] of corroded steels and all of which examine stress-strain and ductility problems and their possible characterization, and some formulas or corresponding derived dependencies are also available in some of them. It is known, that if a mechanical property is changed that means that a stress-strain diagram is changed too. Which means that an elastic strain, plastic strain, strengthening strain and fracture strain will be changed too. The purpose of this study is to establish how ductility is changed on steel with corrosion.

Figure 1 Structure with corroded steel elements

2. ACCELERATED CORROSION METHOD

A widely used method for accelerated corrosion is electrochemical corrosion [4-8]. This method achieves anodic dissolution of the steel by flowing of direct current through the test specimen. The test sample is connected to the positive pole of the power supply (anode) and the negative pole of the power supply is connected to a stainless-steel plate or other inert metal (cathode). It can be stabilized the voltage between the anode and cathode or current through

test specimen. The use of the second option does not require adjustments during accelerated corrosion and allows us approximately to determine daily weight loss [18]. We use a system, developed by us using the current stabilization (the so-called galvanostatic method) to realize accelerated corrosion. Details of the developed system are presented in [22].

We have chosen a current of 600 mA, where the loss of mass for 24 hours determined by the Faraday formula is [22]:

$$\eta[\%] = \frac{100 \times M \times I \times t}{W \times z \times F} = \frac{100 \times 56 \times 0.6 \times 24 \times 60 \times 60}{375 \times 2.5 \times 96484} = 3,21 \%, \quad (1)$$

where $M = 56 \text{ g/mol}$ is the atomic mass of the ferric ion, $I[\text{A}]$ – electric current through the test specimen, $t[\text{s}]$ – time duration of the treatment, $W[\text{g}]$ is the weight of the steel specimen before corrosion treatment, z is the valence of the ferric ion ($z = 2,5$ is the average value for Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions of the corrosion products), $F = 96484 \text{ C/mol}$ is the Faraday constant.

The number of test specimens is 16, separated into two groups. The time duration of the treatment for group A is 14 days and for group B – 5 days. In this case, the approximate percentage weight loss is 50 % for group A and 20 % for group B.

The accelerated corrosion system used consists of 75 adjustable current stabilizers, the current of each of which can be adjusted within the range of 16-200 mA. The system allows parallel connection of current stabilizers. Therefore, a current of 600 mA can be obtained by the parallel connection of three current stabilizers, each set to 200 mA. A block diagram of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 2 [22].

Figure 2 (a) Block scheme of the experimental setup; (b) Photograph of the experimental setup

Weight measurements before corrosion treatment and after corrosion treatment and corrosion products removal are performed with precision balance. Moments of these measurements are shown in Figure 3a and Figure 3b.

Figure 3 (a) Weight measurement of the test specimens before corrosion treatment; (b) Weight measurement of the test specimens after corrosion treatment and corrosion products removal

3. MATERIAL AND STEEL SPECIMEN

3.1. Steel specimen and tensile test

Dimensions of the test specimen depend on many factors. The researchers have chosen what dimensions to be used on their steel specimen [9-12, 15, 18, 22]. We prefer to use a steel specimen which parallel length is a $15d$ [18, 22], because is established that the best and most reliable results are obtained right then [18, 19]. Dimensions and photos of our steel specimen are shown in Figure 4a and Figure 4b.

Figure 4 The used steel specimen – (a) dimensions; (b) photograph

Figure 5 (a) Steel specimens before accelerated corrosion method performing; (b) moment of tensile test of the steel specimen with corrosion

We used a universal testing machine MESSPHYSIK model BETA200-7/6x14 for the tensile test of the steel specimens [18, 22], but according standard ISO 8407:2009 we need to remove

corrosion products (rust) from our samples [6, 18, 22]. We remove corrosion on steel specimens in hydrochloric acid [6, 18, 22] - 10 min, in solution of 500 ml hydrochloric acid with 1000 ml distilled water and 3.5g hexamethylenetetramine on temperature 20 °C [18, 22]. Photograph of a steel specimen after removing corrosion products (rust) is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Photograph of Steel specimen after remove corrosion products (rust)

3.2. Material

Every author using different steel materials, it depends on basic study which is make it [4-18, 22]. Main parts of tank wagon (for example) are design of structural steel S355J2 [20], but the difference between S355JR and S355J2 is that the first have a withstand an impact energy of 27J at +20 °C, the second have withstand an impact energy of 27J at -20 °C, but the stress-strain curve is exactly the same. The steel S355JR is most popular for steel structures in Bulgaria [18, 22]. We prefer to use in our study a structural steel S355JR, as we do [18, 22] with the chemical composition is given on table 1, according standard EN 10025-2-2004. It is known that a chemical element silicon (Si) is given a more strength, but the negative effect is that is reducing a corrosion resistance and elongation and transverse contraction.

Table 1 Chemical composition on steel S355JR

Chemical composition, [%]							
C	Si	Mn	P	S	N	Cu	CEV
max 0.2 4	max 0.55	max 1.6	max 0.04	max 0.04	max 0.01 2	max 0.55	max 0.47

We used a classic stress-strain curve (Figure 7) of S355JR steel and take a main value of strain, which is interest for us.

Figure 7 (a) Stress-strain curve of S355JR steel; (b) main values (points) of ductility

Table 2 Main values from classic stress-stain curve on S355JR steel

main value	elastic strain	plastic strain	strengthening strain	fracture strain
ε , [%]	ε_{el} , [%]	ε_y , [%]	ε_u , [%]	ε_f , [%]
	0.0234	0.6218	1.9025	2.4235
σ , [MPa]	381.6688	368.4887	460.9131	289.2526

4. RESULTS

We have 16 steel specimens, divided in 2 (two) groups – Group A (for 14 days electrochemical accelerated corrosion) and Group B (for 5 days electrochemical accelerated corrosion). The results are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5 (for group A) and Table 6, 7 and 8 (for group B). We use the stochastic method to process [18, 21, 22] the obtained empirical data (main values - strain and stress), as these are random variables [21]. In Figure 8 is show a stress-strain curves (after process of values – stochastic and average) after tensile test on corroded steel specimens and accelerated corrosion results for group A. In Figure 9 is show a stress-strain curves (after process of values – stochastic and average) after tensile test on corroded steel specimens and accelerated corrosion results for group B. Probability of our results – group A is 89.42 % and group B is 88.14 %.

Table 3 Results for group A – strain values

№ of steel specimen	initially weight	final weight	elastic strain	plastic strain	strengthening strain	fracture strain
	(g)	(g)	ε_{el} (%)	ε_y (%)	ε_u (%)	ε_f (%)
1	377.515	204.016	0.167	0.249	0.610	0.741
2	378.757	206.264	0.123	0.532	0.743	0.840
3	367.692	196.750	0.138	0.195	0.382	0.448
4	373.743	201.754	0.125	0.185	0.604	0.705
5	375.559	204.350	0.202	0.335	0.782	0.893
6	381.403	206.096	0.147	0.203	0.520	0.619
7	365.179	199.746	0.292	0.362	0.770	0.854
8	380.162	208.226	0.155	0.207	0.433	0.514
average results	375.001	203.400	0.169	0.284	0.606	0.702
stochastic result	379.385	202.197	0.185	0.353	0.540	0.682

Table 4 Results for group A – stress values

№ of steel specimen	initially weight	final weight	elastic stress σ_{el}	plastic stress σ_y	strengthening (ultimate) stress σ_u	fracture stress σ_f
	(g)	(g)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)
1	377.515	204.016	316.658	345.820	425.354	282.715
2	378.757	206.264	253.461	283.372	373.927	245.437
3	367.692	196.750	289.558	318.841	381.881	260.870
4	373.743	201.754	228.936	234.887	306.942	200.014
5	375.559	204.350	387.649	422.322	502.015	344.117
6	381.403	206.096	249.381	264.701	335.044	223.167
7	365.179	199.746	391.862	427.903	522.666	369.182
8	380.162	208.226	245.196	280.898	348.356	231.000
average results	375.001	203.400	295.338	322.343	399.523	269.563
stochastic result	379.385	202.197	317.846	345.524	413.913	289.916

Table 5 Results for group A – ratio values

ratio values	$\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_u}$	$\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_y}$	$\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_{el}}$	$\frac{\epsilon_u}{\epsilon_y}$	$\frac{\epsilon_u}{\epsilon_{el}}$	$\frac{\epsilon_y}{\epsilon_{el}}$
average results	1.1586	2.4750	4.1567	2.1361	3.5876	1.6795
stochastic result	1.2636	1.9313	3.6933	1.5285	2.9229	1.9123

Table 6 Results for group B – strain values

№ of steel specimen	initially weight	final weight	elastic strain ϵ_{el}	plastic strain ϵ_y	strengthening strain ϵ_u	fracture strain ϵ_f
	(g)	(g)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
9	390.766	327.218	0.278	0.691	1.290	1.549
10	387.051	318.439	0.270	0.757	1.520	1.827
11	387.295	320.102	0.262	0.666	1.293	1.567
12	385.645	318.705	0.189	0.602	1.591	1.916
13	384.358	315.342	0.263	0.647	1.722	2.031
14	380.845	326.442	0.248	0.668	1.336	1.678
15	388.184	341.005	0.233	0.657	1.858	2.202
16	386.449	332.147	0.241	0.656	1.647	1.922
average results	386.324	324.925	0.248	0.668	1.532	1.836
stochastic result	383.844	323.219	0.241	0.663	1.586	1.891

Table 7 Results for group B – stress values

№ of steel specimens	initially weight	final weight	elastic stress σ_{el}	plastic stress σ_y	strengthening (ultimate) stress σ_u	fracture stress σ_f
	(g)	(g)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)
9	390.766	327.218	326.650	372.966	436.589	295.871
10	387.051	318.439	350.962	377.840	437.708	290.284
11	387.295	320.102	349.845	410.079	469.871	314.056
12	385.645	318.705	351.552	368.416	455.750	298.899
13	384.358	315.342	326.809	331.522	413.039	274.232
14	380.845	326.442	301.625	366.499	432.980	281.079
15	388.184	341.005	365.616	360.167	442.127	292.272
16	386.449	332.147	358.474	352.215	438.593	296.102
average results	386.324	324.925	341.442	367.463	440.832	292.849
stochastic result	383.844	323.219	358.920	366.420	450.913	284.414

Table 8 Results for group B – ratio values

ratio values	$\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_u}$	$\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_y}$	$\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_{el}}$	$\frac{\epsilon_u}{\epsilon_y}$	$\frac{\epsilon_u}{\epsilon_{el}}$	$\frac{\epsilon_y}{\epsilon_{el}}$
average results	1.1986	2.7488	7.4038	2.2933	6.1769	2.6935
stochastic result	1.1922	2.8530	7.8530	2.3930	6.5868	2.7525

Figure 8 Results from experiment (group A)

Figure 9 Results from experiment (group B)

5. CONCLUSION

Our experimental results unambiguously established that there was a change in ductility. When corrosion is at an early stage, the change in ductility is small, but with the advancement of corrosion development in steel bearing elements, the change in ductility becomes sensitive. In view of the strength, there is a slight (minor) change which is obviously due to the corrosive effect. The fact that, as corrosive development progresses, the corresponding ductility begins to decrease, it means that there is a correlation between the development of corrosion in a steel bearing element and its ductile qualities. We find that steel elements with corrosion are unable to undergo significant plastic deformations before tearing. It is known that the amount of carbon (C) in a steel spill affects directly the ductility, but in our case, with increasing corrosion, the ductility is reduced. This fact unambiguously supports the thesis that when corrosion enters the steel elements, it directly influences the basic elastic-plastic properties, from the ductile material, becomes a brittle material, although with the look of the chart of ductile material (sometimes).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research received is funding by “Hyosel” Ltd., Sofia, Bulgaria.

REFERENCES

- [1] Budynas, R. G. Shigley's Mechanical Engineering Design, 10th Edition. McGraw Hill, 2015, pp. 233.
- [2] Vernon, J. Introduction to Engineering Materials, 3rd Edition. New York : Industrial Press, 1981.
- [3] Ganev, R. and Godiniachki, G. Steel corpuses destroying from tiredness and stress corrosion. Proceedings of the 5th Scientific Conference Fire and emergency safety 2009, Sofia, Bulgaria, 2009, pp. 190-192.
- [4] Chen, G., Hadi, M., Gao, D. and Zhao, L. Experimental study on the properties of corroded steel fibres. *Construction and Building Materials*, **79**, 2015, pp. 165-172.
- [5] Ponjayuthi, D. and Vinodh, K. Effect of corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel reinforcement, *IJCRR*, **8**(12), 2016, pp. 14-20.
- [6] Chen, H., Zhang, J., Yang, J. and Ye, F. Experimental investigation into corrosion effect on mechanical properties of high strength steel bars under dynamic loadings. *International Journal of Corrosion*, 2018, article number 7169681.
- [7] Zhao, Z. and Fu, L. The probability distribution of pitting for accelerated corrosion reinforcement. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, **9**, 2018, article number e00193.

- [8] Wu, X., Li, L., Li, H., Li, B. and Ling, Z. Effect of strain level on corrosion of stainless steel bar. *Construction and Building Materials*, **163**, 2018, pp. 189-199.
- [9] Kim, I., Dao, D., Jeong, Y., Huh, J. and Ahn, J. Effect of corrosion on the tension behavior of painted structural steel members. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, **133**, 2017, pp. 256-268.
- [10] Sheng, J. and Xia, J. Effect of simulated pitting corrosion on the tensile properties of steel. *Construction and Building Materials*, **131**, 2017, pp. 90-100.
- [11] Qin, G., Xu, S., Yao, D., Zhang, Z. Study on the degradation of mechanical properties of corroded steel plates based on surface topography. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, **125**, 2016, pp. 205-217.
- [12] Chen, H., Zhang, J., Yang, J. and Ye, F. Experimental investigation into corrosion effect in mechanical properties of high strength steel bars under dynamic loading. *International Journal of Corrosion*, 2018, article number 7169681.
- [13] Apostolopoulos, C. and Papadakis, V. Consequences of steel corrosion on the ductility properties of reinforcement bar. *Construction and Building Materials*, **22**, 2008, pp. 2316-2324.
- [14] Hingorani, R., Perez, F., Sanchez, J., Fulla, J., Andrade, C. and Tanner, P. Loss of ductility and strength of reinforcing steel due to pitting corrosion. Proceedings of the VIII International Conference on Fracture Mechanics of Concrete and Concrete Structures: FraMCoS-8, Toledo, Spain, 2013.
- [15] Burke, St. and Bruneau, M. Effect of Surface Roughness on Cyclic Ductility of Corroded Steel. *Journal of Structural engineering*, **142**(6), 2016, article number 04016014.
- [16] Gathimba, N. and Kitane, Y. Static ductility evaluation of corroded steel plates considering surface roughness characteristics. Proceedings of the The 2018 Structures Congress (Structures18), Songdo Convensia, Incheon, Korea, 2018, pp. 27-31.
- [17] Moreno, E., Cobo Al. and Gonzalez M. Effect of corrosion degree on different steel ductility parameters, based on "Equivalent Steel" criterion. *International Journal of Structural Integrity*, **7**(2), 2016, pp. 260-276.
- [18] Shopov, A.; Bonev, B. Experimental study of zone of yield strength on corroded construction steel specimens for reuse. Proceedings of the 10th Anniversary International Scientific Conference Building defects 2018, Ceske Budejovice, Czech Republic, 2018, pp.161-167.
- [19] Podskrebko, M. Strength of materials, Minsk : Vishaya shkola, 2007, in Russian.
- [20] Stastniak, P., Moravcik, M. and Smetanka L. Investigation of strength conditions of the new wagon prototype type Zans. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, **254**, 2019, article number 02037.
- [21] Shopov, A. Stochastic way for calculation of strength on construction steel with corrosion. Proceedings of the XVIII Anniversary International Scientific Conference by Construction and Architecture VSU'2018, Sofia, Bulgaria, 2018, pp. 413-418.
- [22] Shopov, A., Bonev, B. Change of young's module on steel specimens with corrosion by experiment, *International Journal of Modeling and Optimization* (in press).